

FROM ENFORCEMENT TO ENGAGEMENT: EXAMINING THE IMPACT OF COMMUNITY POLICING ON COMMUNAL CONFLICT IN LAGOS METROPOLIS

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Community policing, communal conflict, Lagos Metropolis, crime prevention, public trust, intelligence gathering.

Abstract: *This study examines the impact of community policing on communal conflict in Lagos Metropolis. It explores how community policing influences crime detection, conflict resolution, trust between the police and the public, intelligence gathering, and overall public safety. Using a structured questionnaire administered to 376 respondents including community leaders and residents the study finds that community policing has significantly improved crime detection, strengthened police–community relationships, and enhanced intelligence sharing. The findings also reveal a marked reduction in communal conflicts, with community-based security initiatives playing a key role in dispute mediation and peacebuilding. Although challenges persist, particularly in the partial implementation of Model Police Stations and inadequate officer training, the overall framework has been effective in fostering security and social stability. The study recommends full operationalization of Model Police Stations, greater community engagement through town halls, enhanced police training, and improved support for the Lagos State Neighborhood Safety Corps. These measures will deepen the impact of community policing and sustain peace within the metropolis.*

Introduction

Urban communal conflicts have emerged as one of the most persistent security challenges in contemporary societies. As cities become more diverse and densely populated, underlying tensions over ethnicity, religion, resources, and governance frequently erupt into violence that threatens peace and development (Kelling &

Wilson, 2018). Lagos Nigeria’s commercial nerve center and Africa’s fastest-growing megacity embodies this complexity. Its population of over twenty-five million people, drawn from diverse ethnic and cultural groups, experiences periodic communal clashes, especially in areas such as Ikorodu, Mushin, Mile 12, and Ajah (Oluwalogbon, 2024). These conflicts often stem

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from land disputes, political rivalries, and resource competition, worsened by unemployment and poor governance.

Conventional policing methods have proven inadequate in addressing these multifaceted conflicts. The reactive, enforcement-driven approach often focuses on suppressing violence rather than preventing it. In response, community policing has emerged as a proactive and participatory strategy that emphasizes collaboration between law enforcement and the people. It shifts policing from a control-based model to a trust-based partnership where both parties jointly identify and resolve the causes of insecurity (Oshita et al., 2019). Meanwhile, the theoretical foundations of community policing draw from Broken Windows Theory (Kelling & Wilson, 2018), which emphasizes the need to maintain social order to prevent larger crimes, and Social Conflict Theory (Oberschall, 1978), which attributes community unrest to structural inequalities and resource imbalances. Together, these theories justify a policing model that engages directly with communities to resolve conflicts before they escalate.

Lagos State has adopted several community policing initiatives, including neighborhood watch groups, joint patrols, and community forums, supported by the Lagos State Security Trust Fund (LSSTF). Despite progress, challenges such as inadequate officer training, weak coordination, and lingering public distrust

continue to undermine effectiveness. While community policing has been studied in rural and semi-urban Nigeria (Osayekemwen & Adeoluwa, 2022; Paki & Rufus, 2023), limited attention has been given to its impact in metropolitan contexts like Lagos. This study therefore investigates the influence of community policing on communal conflict in Lagos Metropolis.

However, Lagos Metropolis continues to experience recurrent communal conflicts that endanger public safety, disrupt economic activities, and threaten social cohesion. These conflicts often arising from ethnic rivalries, land disputes, and political tensions—have become increasingly violent and destructive (Adejoh, 2013). Despite the efforts of security agencies, conventional policing remains largely reactive, emphasizing law enforcement over conflict prevention.

Community policing was introduced to bridge this gap by promoting collaboration and mutual trust between police and communities. However, in Lagos, implementation has been inconsistent due to inadequate training, limited resources, and enduring public skepticism toward law enforcement (Ambali & Araba, 2020). Although several initiatives exist, their real impact on mitigating communal conflict has not been adequately examined. This gap underscores the need for an empirical study on how community policing influences communal harmony,

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intelligence gathering, and grassroots conflict resolution in Lagos Metropolis.

Research Objectives

The study's main objective is to assess the impact of community policing on communal conflict in Lagos Metropolis. The specific objectives are to:

1. Examine the forms and structure of community policing initiatives implemented in Lagos Metropolis.
2. Assess the impact of community policing on communal conflict resolution and intelligence gathering.
3. Evaluate how community policing influences trust, collaboration, and security partnerships between the police and residents.

Justification of the Study

This study is significant for both academic and policy reasons. First, it contributes to the growing body of literature on security governance by providing empirical insights into the urban dynamics of community policing in Nigeria's largest city. Existing research has focused mainly on rural contexts, leaving a knowledge gap in understanding how community policing operates in a densely populated, heterogeneous environment like Lagos.

Second, the findings offer practical guidance for policymakers, especially the Lagos State Government and Nigeria Police Force, on how to strengthen community-police collaboration for sustainable peace. By identifying gaps in

implementation and success factors, the study provides a foundation for reforming local security architecture.

Finally, the study has social value. It promotes citizen participation in security management and highlights how inclusive policing can enhance community resilience, trust, and peaceful coexistence key ingredients for urban development and stability.

Conceptual and Literature Review

Concept of Community Policing

Community policing represents a paradigm shift from the traditional enforcement-centered model to a partnership-based approach emphasizing prevention, dialogue, and mutual trust. According to Schaffer (2023), it is a philosophy that integrates community participation into every aspect of policing to address the causes of crime and disorder rather than their symptoms. Skogan (2019) identifies three essential components: community partnerships, organizational transformation, and problem-solving. Through these, police officers work closely with residents to identify local safety concerns, analyze underlying causes, and develop tailored solutions.

Officers are often embedded within neighborhoods to foster familiarity and personal relationships with residents. Regular town hall meetings, patrols, and joint initiatives encourage shared responsibility for community safety. Otuu (2024) emphasizes that the success of this model

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depends on transparency, accountability, and inclusivity.

Community Policing and Communal Conflict in Nigeria

Community policing in Nigeria emerged as a reform-oriented response to the growing crisis of insecurity, communal clashes, and citizen distrust in conventional policing institutions. The traditional law enforcement system—centralized, reactive, and often coercive—proved increasingly ineffective in managing the complex security realities of a multi-ethnic and socioeconomically diverse nation (Oshita et al., 2019). Rising incidents of ethnic violence, farmer–herder conflicts, and urban criminality throughout the late 1990s and early 2000s prompted the federal government to rethink its security architecture. Consequently, under the administration of President Olusegun Obasanjo, community policing was officially introduced as part of broader police reforms aimed at decentralizing authority, enhancing public trust, and embedding law enforcement within local communities.

This policy shift reflected an understanding that policing cannot succeed through force alone, but through partnership, dialogue, and mutual accountability. The model was designed to empower communities to participate actively in identifying and addressing the underlying causes of crime and communal tension, thereby complementing the efforts of the Nigerian Police

Force (NPF). Supported by donor agencies and civil society organizations, the early implementation stages involved pilot projects in selected states such as Enugu, Kaduna, Kano, and Lagos. These initiatives promoted local security committees, police–community liaison officers, and conflict-resolution platforms that integrated traditional leaders and civic groups into the security process.

Successes

Despite initial skepticism, community policing in Nigeria has recorded notable achievements, particularly in intelligence gathering, crime prevention, and peacebuilding at the grassroots level. One of its most significant impacts has been the restoration of trust and communication between citizens and law enforcement officers. By involving residents in security decision-making and patrol structures, community policing has helped bridge the historical divide between police and the people.

In Lagos State, the establishment of the Lagos Neighborhood Safety Corps (LNSC) stands as a major success story. The Corps works hand-in-hand with formal police units to monitor neighborhoods, mediate minor disputes, and provide intelligence on potential threats (Oluwalogbon, 2024). This grassroots engagement has resulted in a more responsive and preventive form of security management. Similarly, Ordu and Nnam (2017) observe that community policing initiatives have improved

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early conflict detection mechanisms, allowing for swift intervention before disputes escalate into violence. Ambali and Araba (2020) further report that crime rates declined in areas where community policing structures were operational, attributing this success to enhanced information sharing and localized decision-making.

In rural and peri-urban communities, the adoption of community policing principles has also strengthened cooperation between law enforcement and traditional institutions. Chiefs, religious leaders, and youth associations now play advisory or liaison roles in maintaining peace, reflecting a hybrid model that merges modern policing with indigenous conflict-resolution systems. These partnerships have not only improved surveillance but have also legitimized the police in the eyes of previously distrustful communities.

Challenges

However, the successes of community policing in Nigeria are counterbalanced by deep-seated challenges that continue to constrain its effectiveness. Foremost among these is inadequate funding. Most community policing initiatives rely heavily on state or donor support, making them vulnerable to political changes and inconsistent resource allocation (Mohammed & Zamani, 2023). Without sustained financial investment, critical components such as logistics, communication equipment, and officer training suffer neglect.

Inadequate capacity building also undermines the quality of implementation. Many police officers assigned to community policing units lack the necessary skills in mediation, cultural sensitivity, and community engagement. This has led to cases where interactions between police and residents are marred by misunderstanding or hostility, eroding the very trust the program seeks to build.

Another persistent challenge is ethnic and political bias in law enforcement operations. Paki and Rufus (2023) note that Nigeria's diverse ethnic composition often influences how security interventions are perceived and executed. In some cases, community policing structures are viewed as favoring dominant ethnic groups or political interests, thereby reproducing the same mistrust they were designed to eliminate. Furthermore, weak coordination and fragmented implementation across states have limited the program's impact. While some regions have integrated community policing into broader security strategies, others treat it as a parallel or ad hoc initiative, leading to inconsistency in outcomes.

A critical obstacle remains the fear of reprisals among citizens who share intelligence with security agencies. As Kpae and Eric (2017) observe, the absence of robust witness protection mechanisms discourages community members from reporting criminal or violent activities. This fear is amplified in areas where gangs or armed

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groups exert influence, making community policing officers themselves targets of intimidation. However, institutional corruption and bureaucratic inertia within the Nigerian Police Force weaken accountability and morale. Without transparent monitoring systems or incentives for officers to uphold community values, the philosophy of community policing risks being reduced to rhetoric rather than practice.

Regional Approaches to Community Policing in Nigeria

Community policing varies across Nigeria's geopolitical zones, reflecting regional security realities:

- **Southwest:** *Amotekun Corps* integrates traditional vigilantes and formal policing structures to address banditry and herder-farmer clashes (Olatunbosun, 2023).
- **North:** Vigilante groups like *Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF)* supplement military operations against insurgency, though often without legal frameworks (Bawa, 2023).
- **Middle Belt:** Ethnic vigilantes in Plateau and Benue mediate land and religious conflicts but operate informally (Ojo et al., 2023).
- **Southeast:** *Neighborhood Watch* initiatives in Anambra and Enugu formalize local security structures and have proven effective in crime reduction (Ikechukwu, 2021; Aleyomi & Nwagwu, 2023).

These diverse models highlight the adaptability of community policing but also underscore the need for standardized implementation and stronger institutional oversight.

The reviewed literature underscores that community policing can significantly reduce communal conflict by promoting trust, intelligence sharing, and joint problem-solving. However, in Lagos Metropolis where socioeconomic diversity and rapid urbanization create unique security challenges its success depends on effective training, funding, and institutional reforms that strengthen citizen-police cooperation.

Theoretical Review

The theoretical underpinning of this study is predicated on the Broken Windows Theory, introduced by Kelling and Wilson in 1982. The theory argues that unchecked minor offenses create an atmosphere of lawlessness, which encourages further violations. According to Kelling and Wilson (1982), maintaining urban spaces in orderly and well-maintained state sends a clear message that public order is valued, thereby discouraging crime and promoting societal stability.

This theory emphasizes the significance of addressing minor disruptions before they escalate into more severe criminal behavior (Kelling & Wilson, 1982). By addressing small-scale crimes early enough, communities can prevent the breakdown of social order and

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discourage more serious crimes from taking root. The approach aligns with community policing strategies that prioritize early intervention and visible enforcement of laws. As such, an environment is created where individuals feel a shared responsibility for maintaining public order.

In the context of communal conflict, the Broken Windows theory suggests that neglecting early signs of disorder, whether social or physical, can lead to deterioration of social cohesion and the emergence of large-scale conflicts. The theory implies that resolving minor disputes, addressing grievances, and maintaining open communication channels within communities are essential to prevent escalation of conflicts.

Empirical Review

Several studies have examined the effectiveness of community policing in preventing and resolving conflicts in various parts of Nigeria.

Ambali and Araba (2020) found that LNSC contributed positively to crime reduction and public safety in Lagos State. However, they maintained the importance of better training, resourcing and tools to further improve effectiveness. Focusing on Ikorodu and Badagry local government areas, Osakede, et al., (2016) argued that community policing strengthened internal security in these areas. Similarly, Adejoh (2013) found that informal security structures played a significant role in preventing crime within Lagos neighborhoods. Furthermore,

Oluwalogbon (2024)'s findings show that LNSC's community-centric approach has led to a decline in crime rates within Lagos metropolis but faced challenges that limit its effectiveness. Findings of Shittu, et al. (2023) showed that technology-driven and community-based policing strategies were the most effective in combating crime in Lagos.

Furthermore, studies conducted in other states revealed that while community policing has led to better management of conflict, challenges persist. Isaac, et al. (2023) found that community policing in Chika and Lugbe significantly improved security, with intelligence gathering and surveillance being pivotal to proactive responses to security threats. Adelani, et al. (2023) highlighted a poor synergy between law enforcement law enforcement and local communities in Kubwa, Bwari Area Council, and argued for decentralization of security powers to enable local governments have more control over policing in their areas.

Findings from Osayekemwen and Adeoluwa (2022) corroborated the positive impact of community policing, using Osun State as a case study, and advocated increased community engagement to increase its effectiveness. Basiru (2019) found that the introduction of community policing especially joint patrols, have significantly improved security in Oyo state, with local communities also taking proactive steps such as forming vigilante groups and street

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patrols, to prevent crimes. Kenneth, et al. (2023) assessed community policing outfits – including Amotekun in Southwest, and confirmed its positive contributions to national security. Their study made case for the formal integration of informal policing structures into national security framework.

Garba and Maigida (2020) investigated community policing in Bauchi Local Government Area, finding it effective in crime prevention through a strong relationship between the police and local communities. The study also highlighted the proactive role of vigilante groups and street patrols in crime control.

Overall, the studies reviewed highlight the positive impact of community policing on security across various Nigerian regions. They emphasize the effectiveness of community-based security outfits in reducing crime, improving public safety, and fostering stronger police-community relationships. However, challenges such as inadequate funding, poor training, corruption, and lack of collaboration between law enforcement and local communities were also identified. The studies argue for decentralizing security control, enhancing community engagement, and better equipping and empowering local security outfits like Amotekun and the LNSC. There is also a call for integrating these community policing structures into the national security framework to strengthen overall security in Nigeria.

Research Design and Methodology

This study adopts a case study research design to facilitate a detailed and context-specific understanding of community policing initiatives within the Lagos Metropolis. The case study approach allows for the exploration of complex social realities within their natural settings, emphasizing the interplay between institutional structures, community participation, and local security practices (Saunders et al., 2019). By focusing on Lagos a microcosm of Nigeria's urban security challenges the study aims to generate practical insights applicable to broader national and sub-Saharan African contexts. A quantitative research approach was employed to ensure objectivity and enable statistical interpretation of the findings. Data were collected through a structured close-ended questionnaire designed to elicit measurable responses on perceptions, implementation, and outcomes of community policing strategies. The instrument was organized into four sections: the first captured respondents' demographic profiles (such as gender, years of residence, and stakeholder category); the second identified the forms and extent of community policing initiatives across various localities; the third assessed perceptions of their operational effectiveness; while the final section focused on outcomes related to conflict management and community safety.

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The study area, Lagos Metropolis, represents Nigeria's largest urban agglomeration and economic hub. It is characterized by rapid urbanization, cultural diversity, and significant socio-economic inequality, all of which contribute to complex patterns of insecurity and community tension. The metropolis comprises twenty local government areas (LGAs), including Ikeja, Eti-Osa, Lagos Island, Surulere, and Kosofe each with distinct demographic, infrastructural, and security profiles. With an estimated population of 25 million people (National Bureau of Statistics, 2023), Lagos provides a compelling case for studying community-based security arrangements in dense urban environments.

A purposive sampling technique was adopted to identify respondents who possess relevant knowledge and direct engagement with community security issues. The sampling frame included community leaders, property owners, tenants, religious leaders, and local government official's stakeholders who interact regularly with law enforcement and experience the

outcomes of community policing. Twenty participants were selected from each of the twenty LGAs, yielding a total sample size of 400 respondents. This sample size ensured adequate representation of key community perspectives across diverse socio-economic backgrounds.

To ensure the credibility and ethical soundness of the study, standard ethical procedures were rigorously observed. Informed consent was obtained from all participants after a full disclosure of the research objectives and their rights as respondents. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were assured of privacy, confidentiality, and the right to withdraw at any time. Anonymity was maintained throughout data collection and reporting to protect participants' identities and foster honest responses.

Analysis of Results and Discussion of Findings

Out of 400 distributed questionnaires, 376 were validly completed and returned, representing a high response rate of 94%, which strengthens the reliability and generalizability of the findings.

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Demographic Attributes of Participants

Option	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male: 230	61%
	Female: 146	39%
Length of Stay	Below 5 years: 88	23%
	5–10 years: 186	49%
	Above 10 years: 102	27%
Stakeholder Type	Community Leaders: 130	35%
	Landlords/Property Owners: 120	32%
	Tenants/Residents: 80	21%
	Religious Leaders: 22	6%
	Local Government Officials: 24	6%

Interpretation:

The demographic profile indicates that men constitute a higher proportion of respondents (61%), which may reflect male dominance in community leadership and decision-making structures in Lagos. Over 70% of participants have lived in their communities for five years or more, implying strong familiarity with local

security arrangements and social dynamics. Community leaders and landlords together represent the largest stakeholder categories, suggesting that those with influence and property-based stakes play active roles in community policing and conflict resolution initiatives.

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION OF RESULTS

Objective 1: Examine the Forms and Structure of Community Policing Initiatives Implemented in Lagos Metropolis

Forms/Structure of Community Policing	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
Police–Community Forums (PCFs)	4.35	0.68	Very High
Community Safety Partnerships	4.10	0.72	High
Neighborhood Watch Committees	3.85	0.80	High
Joint Patrols and Surveillance Teams	3.60	0.83	Moderate
Volunteer Policing and Youth Vigilance Groups	3.40	0.91	Moderate
Local Security Meetings and Peace Councils	4.20	0.74	High
Intelligence Reporting Channels (Hotlines/Apps)	3.75	0.79	High

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Interpretation:

The results indicate that the most dominant form of community policing in Lagos is the Police–Community Forum, with a mean score of 4.35, showing very high respondent agreement. This suggests that frequent meetings and dialogue between police and community representatives have become institutionalized mechanisms for grassroots security management. Similarly, Community Safety Partnerships ($\bar{x} = 4.10$) and

Local Peace Councils ($\bar{x} = 4.20$) reflect collaborative structures that enhance preventive policing. The relatively moderate ratings for Volunteer Policing ($\bar{x} = 3.40$) and Joint Patrols ($\bar{x} = 3.60$) suggest operational or resource limitations in sustaining such initiatives. Lagos exhibits a multi-layered and semi-formal structure of community policing, combining official frameworks and citizen-led vigilance groups.

Objective 2: Assess the Impact of Community Policing on Communal Conflict Resolution and Intelligence Gathering

Impact Indicators	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
Reduction in Local Disputes	4.25	0.64	High
Speed of Conflict Mediation	4.00	0.71	High
Timely Intelligence Gathering	4.30	0.66	Very High
Prevention of Crime Escalation	4.10	0.74	High
Responsiveness to Community Complaints	3.80	0.85	Moderate
Coordination between Vigilantes and Police	3.65	0.83	Moderate

Interpretation:

Respondents largely agree that community policing has had a significant positive impact on conflict resolution and intelligence gathering. The highest mean score (4.30) for Timely Intelligence Gathering reflects enhanced flow of local information to formal police networks, improving preventive responses to security threats. The results also reveal a strong contribution to conflict de-escalation and local

dispute resolution, aligning with Lagos’ history of neighborhood mediation systems. However, the moderate perception of responsiveness ($\bar{x} = 3.80$) and vigilante-police coordination ($\bar{x} = 3.65$) suggests that operational synergy and institutional trust still need strengthening. Statistically, the average composite mean ($\bar{x} = 4.02$) confirms that community policing initiatives have a strong impact on intelligence-led policing and community peacebuilding.

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Objective 3: Evaluate How Community Policing Influences Trust, Collaboration, and Security Partnerships between the Police and Residents

Trust and Collaboration Indicators	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Dev.	Interpretation
Police Transparency and Accountability	3.70	0.81	Moderate
Resident Willingness to Report Crimes	4.15	0.70	High
Mutual Respect between Police and Citizens	3.85	0.76	High
Perceived Fairness in Policing	3.50	0.89	Moderate
Level of Public Engagement in Security Dialogues	4.05	0.74	High
Trust in Police Presence and Patrols	3.95	0.78	High

Interpretation:

The findings demonstrate that community policing has moderately strengthened trust and collaboration between residents and the police. Respondents scored Resident Willingness to Report Crimes ($\bar{x} = 4.15$) and Public Engagement in Security Dialogues ($\bar{x} = 4.05$) highly, showing a shift toward participatory security culture. However, Perceived Fairness ($\bar{x} = 3.50$) and Transparency ($\bar{x} = 3.70$) remain lower, highlighting lingering skepticism about police accountability. These results imply that while community policing has improved communication and cooperative security frameworks, it still faces institutional credibility and consistency gaps.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the dynamics, effectiveness, and relational impacts of community policing initiatives within Lagos Metropolis. The analysis revealed that community policing in Lagos is built on a hybrid structure, blending formal police–community partnerships with informal

neighborhood vigilance groups and civil mediation mechanisms. These initiatives have become central to maintaining urban peace and preventing crime in a rapidly growing city with complex social networks.

The results clearly show that community policing has had a high positive impact on communal conflict resolution and intelligence gathering, with a mean score of 4.02. This implies that information sharing, early warning systems, and grassroots engagement have strengthened proactive policing and reduced the escalation of local disputes. However, despite these successes, there remain institutional and operational constraints including irregular coordination between formal police units and community vigilantes, uneven trust levels, and inadequate logistics support for joint patrol activities.

Furthermore, while community policing has enhanced citizen collaboration and public participation, the findings indicate moderate confidence in police transparency and fairness. This reveals that sustainable community security

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must go beyond collaboration to include consistent accountability mechanisms that reassure residents of equal justice and professional conduct by law enforcement agents. In sum, community policing has emerged as a strategic model for participatory urban security governance in Lagos. Yet, to achieve its full potential, it must evolve from ad hoc cooperation to institutionalized partnerships backed by adequate resources, mutual accountability, and continued civic education.

Recommendations

- 1. Institutionalize Community Policing Frameworks:** The Lagos State Government and the Nigeria Police Force should formalize community policing structures through a legally backed state framework that clearly defines the roles of all participants including vigilante groups, traditional rulers, and civil society representatives.
- 2. Strengthen Intelligence and Information Systems:** Invest in secure digital reporting platforms, hotlines, and neighborhood data systems that can make intelligence gathering faster, confidential, and verifiable. This will enhance pre-emptive response to threats and reduce reliance on informal rumor networks.
- 3. Enhance Police–Community Trust through Transparency:** Regular town-hall briefings, public accountability sessions, and the publication of policing outcomes will help

rebuild confidence and dispel mistrust. Trust grows when communities see measurable improvements and open dialogue from security agencies.

4. Capacity Building and Joint Training Programs: Both police officers and community volunteers should receive joint training on mediation, human rights, early warning systems, and crisis communication. This will promote professionalism and shared understanding of roles.

5. Provide Sustainable Funding and Logistics: Community policing committees should not rely solely on community donations. Dedicated budgetary allocations from the state's security trust fund can ensure regular patrols, communication tools, and maintenance of surveillance infrastructure.

6. Integrate Traditional Conflict Resolution Mechanisms: Given Lagos' diverse communities, indigenous conflict resolution systems (e.g., elders' councils, neighborhood peace committees) should be integrated into the policing framework to strengthen legitimacy and cultural relevance.

7. Monitor and Evaluate Performance Regularly: Establish measurable indicators such as reduction in crime rates, response time to reports, and citizen satisfaction levels to periodically assess the effectiveness of community policing programs and ensure data-driven adjustments.

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8. Encourage Youth and Women

Participation: Including youth groups and women associations in local security forums will not only expand community representation but also enhance intelligence access from underrepresented segments of the population.

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9. Promote Inter-Agency

Collaboration: Coordination between the Nigeria Police Force, Lagos Neighborhood Safety Agency (LNSA), and local vigilante networks should be institutionalized to avoid duplication of efforts and improve joint operations.

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